

Quiz Algorithmic Thinking (JAVA)

11-12-2015

[4p] Question 1.

Take a look at the signature below and answer the following questions:

```
public void jump( int distance )
```

- a. What is the method's name?
- b. What is the parameter type?
- c. What does **void** mean?
- d. What parameter type is used for text?

[4p] Question 2.

Fill in the correct text for A, B, C and D in the flowchart.

Note: Dodo must be on top of the egg in order to hatch it.

- A) _____
- B) _____
- C) _____
- D) _____

Question 3.

Footstep trees! Footstep trees are made according to following algorithm (or step-by-step plan):

These are the steps for a one-tree :	
Take one step forward and leave a footprint. Then take one step back.	
We now know the footstep-program of a one-tree. The program for a two-tree looks like this:	
Take two steps forward leaving a footprint with each step taken. Then: Turn +45 degrees and do a one-tree. Turn -90 degrees and do a one-tree. Turn +45 degrees and take two steps back (leaving no additional footprints).	
The footstep-program for a three-tree can be explained easily, because a three-tree contains several two-trees	
Go three steps forward, leaving a footprint with each step taken. Then: Turn +45 degrees and do a two-tree. Turn -90 degrees and do a two-tree. Turn +45 degrees and take three steps back (leaving no additional footprints).	
The footstep-program for a four-tree follows the same scheme.	

[3p] a) Give an algorithm for creating a four-tree. Do this in the same way as the algorithm for the three-tree above.

[2p] b) According to the plan, which of the following trees is a four-tree? Circle the answer.

[3p]

c) Let's change the structure of tree as shown in the figure to the right. As you can see, it now has three subtrees instead of two 2-subtrees. Write an algorithm for drawing the **new-three-tree** so that it will produce the figure on the right.

Question 4.

In Greenfoot the 'RUN' button is pressed with the following code in the act method:

```
public void act( ){
    if( canMove( ) ) {
        move( );
    } else {
        if ( ! foundEgg( ) ) {
            layEgg( );
        }
    }
}
```

[2p] a) Draw the corresponding flowchart.

[2p] b) What is the purpose or the outcome of this piece of code?

- I. Find out whether or not Dodo can move;
 - II. Help Dodo reach the edge of the world;
 - III. Dodo reaches the edge of the world and lays an egg;
 - IV. Make Dodo lay an egg after every step.
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